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FORMULATION, CHARACTERIZATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL COLD CREAM

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ABSTRACT

Herbal cosmetic are the preparation which are used to beautify and enhance the human appearances. The aim of present work is to formulate, evaluate and characterization of Curcumin, Ashwagandha and Neem containing Herbal cold cream. The Curcumin, Ashwagandha and Neem containing Herbal cold cream is prepared by water in oil method by using suitable base for the purpose of nourishing and moisturizing the skin. The herbal extract containing cold cream gives cooling and soothing effect due to slow evaporation of water present in emulsion. The prepared herbal cold creams are characterized for production yields, DSC and SEM. The production yields of formulations were from 78.4% to 87.5%. DSC studies are revealed that the drug and base are compatible with each other during preparation. The changes in physical properties of the formulated creams were not observed. The formulated cream shows good consistency and spreadability, homogeneity, pH, non-greasy and no evidence of phase separation during study period. Stability parameters like visual appearance, nature, viscosity and fragrance of formulated creams showed that there was no significant variation during the study period. All nine herbal cold cream formulations showed significant activities. Based on the results, we can suggest that all the nine formulations F1, F2, F3, F4, F5, F6, F7, F8 and F9 were stable and can be safely used on the skin.

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INTRODUCTION

Skin is the outer covering of the body. In human, it is the largest organ of the integumentary system. The skin is making up 12-15% of body weight and with a surface area of 1-2m². Skin is composed of three layers such as Epidermis, Dermis, Hypodermis or Subcutis. The three layers of the skin form an effective barrier to the external environment, allow the transmission of sensory information, and serve a significant role in maintaining homeostasis.^[1] Healthy, young vital skin is usually able to maintain sufficient moisture. In dry skin, the barrier function may be insufficient owing to a variety of reasons. Although anyone can develop dry skin, the condition is more prone in the 65-year and older age groups; in those who live in dry, cold, or low-humidity climates; and in those who bath or shower very frequently. Although most cases of dry skin are caused by environmental exposures, certain diseases can also significantly alter the function and appearance of the skin.^[2]

The word "Cosmetics" means, any substances intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, sprayed or applied to any part of human body for the purpose of cleaning, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance. Herbal cosmetics are the preparation, which represents cosmetics associated with active bioactive ingredients or pharmaceuticals. The use of phytochemicals from a variety of botanicals have dual functions, they serve as cosmetics for the care of body and its parts and the botanical ingredients present influence biological function of skin and provide nutrients necessary for the healthy skin or hair.^[3] Herbal cosmetics are made from original ingredients in plants, leaves, roots, fruits and flowers which have properties for health and beauty. Major chemical compounds in plants are alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids, steroids, tannins and saponins which can be assessed by phytochemicals screening. Herbs serve as important cosmeceuticals as they do not carry any adverse effects.^[4]

Cream is defined as semisolid emulsions which are oil in water (o/w) or water in oil (w/o) type and these semisolid emulsions are intended for external application. Cream is classified as oil in water and water in oil emulsion.^[5] Cold cream is an emulsion of water and certain fats, usually including beeswax and various scent agents, designed to smooth skin and remove make up. Basically, cold cream is an oil-in-water type (o/w) of emulsion. After the creams are rubbed on the skin, a sufficient quantity of the water evaporates to impart a phase inversion to the water-in-oil type. The solvent action of the oil, as external phase, imparts the cleansing properly. In beeswax-borax type preparation borax reacts with the free fatty acid present in the beeswax and produces soft soap which act as the emulsifying agent and emulsifies the oil phase, containing beeswax, mineral oil, paraffin etc., in the aqueous phase. The main principle of cold cream involves slow evaporation of water phase which leads to cooling sensation. On storage, phase inversion occurs and water-in-oil emulsion cream is formed and this is often known as cold cream. On application, due to evaporation of water, cold sensation is observed; hence, it is called cold cream. Oily film remaining on the skin gives emollient action and protection to the skin.^[6]

Advantages of herbal cold cream

- Ease of application.
- Convenient to all the population.
- Avoidance of risk.
- In case of intra and inter-patient variations, avoid fluctuation of drug levels.
- No special risk or technician required for application of product.
- Achievement of efficacy with lower total daily dosage of drug.
- High patient compliance.

Disadvantages of herbal cold cream

- Larger particle sized drugs cannot be easily absorbed through the skin pores.
- Chances of skin irritation of contact dermatitis due to any drug interactions.
- Poor absorption may result due to the poor permeability of some drugs through the skin.
- Chances of allergic reaction.
- It can be used mainly for drug which required very small plasma concentration for action.
- Denaturation of the drugs takes place due to the presence of an enzyme in epidermis.^[7]

Following are the objectives of the proposed work:

- To formulate herbal cold cream using suitable bases in different ratios and suitable method.
- To characterize the morphological features of prepared herbal cold cream.
- To evaluate the prepared herbal cold cream. The evaluation parameters are as follow,
 - a) **Homogeneity & Appearance**
 - b) Organoleptic evaluation
 - c) Washability
 - d) pH
 - e) Viscosity
 - f) Irritancy test
- To carry out the drug release, consistency and spreadability study from the prepared herbal cold cream.

Therefore, present work aims on formulate, characterize and evaluate the herbal cold cream by using suitable base.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Materials**

Drugs such as Curcumin, Ashwagandha and Neem are purchased from Sridevi Ayurvedic store, Chitradurga. All the other chemicals used in formulation are of analytical grades from local chemical distributors.

Table No: 1. Ingredients used to prepare herbal cold cream.

Sl. No.	Ingredients	Suppliers
1	Beeswax	SD Fine chemicals Ltd.
2	Borax	SD Fine chemicals Ltd.
3	Liquid paraffin	SD Fine chemicals Ltd.
4	Cetyl alcohol	Yarrow Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.
5	Methyl paraben	Yarrow Chemicals Pvt. Ltd.
6	Perfume	Nice chemicals Pvt. Ltd

Table No: 2. Equipment used in the preparation of herbal cold cream.

Sl. No.	Equipment name	Manufactured by
1	UV visible spectrophotometer	Shimadzu (1700)
2	Brookfield viscometer	Analytical technologies
3	Digital pH meter	Analytical technologies
4	Magnetic stirrer	Analytical technologies

Preparation of herbal cold cream**Table No: 3. Formulation Table of Herbal Cold Cream.**

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
	Curcumin			Ashwagandha			Neem		
Drug (gm)	50	100	150	50	100	150	50	100	150
Beeswax (gm)	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Liquid paraffin (ml)	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25	25
Cetyl alcohol (gm)	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52
Borax (gm)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	20.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Methyl paraben (gm)	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
Water (ml)	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6	16.6
Perfume (ml), Qs to 50gm	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs	Qs

Formulation of herbal cold cream involves three steps**i. Step one preparation of aqueous phase**

In a 50 ml of beaker 16.6ml of water, 0.2g of Borax and 0.1 ml of methyl paraben is added and heated up to 75 °C by using water bath.

ii. Step two preparation of oil phase

Simultaneously, 8 gm of bees wax, 25 ml of liquid paraffin and 0.52 gm of cetyl alcohol are added in porcelain china dish separately and melted up to 75°C by using water bath.

iii. Step three mixing of both the phases

To an oil phase, aqueous phase is added drop wise with constant stirring until it comes to 45 to 50°C. Then, to this mixture the Herbal Drug and perfume are added with constant stirring.

Characterization of herbal cold cream**Percentage yield**

The prepared herbal cold cream of all batches were accurately weighed. The measured weight of prepared herbal cold cream were divided by total amount of all the excipients and drug used in the preparation of the herbal cold cream gives the total percentage of herbal cold creams. It was calculated by the following equation.

$$\text{Percentage yield} = \frac{\text{Actual weight of the product}}{\text{Total weight of the excipients and drug}} \times 100$$

Morphology study using SEM

The morphological studies were carried out by ZEISS EVO. US Scanning electron microscope (SEM), connected with fine coat, JEOL JFC-1100E Ion sputter. The sample was loaded on copper sample holder and sputter coated with carbon followed by Gold.

Morphological study using DSC

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) study was carried out to evaluate thermal behavior and thermo tropic characteristic of the drug. Nearly 5mg sample (Curcumin F3, Ashwagandha F6 and Neem F9) were sealed in aluminum pan followed by heating at a rate of 10⁰ C/min over temperature range of 40-300⁰C under nitrogen atmosphere of flow rate 10ml/min and thermogram (Mettler-Toledo DSC 821e Switzerland) was obtained.

Evaluation of Herbal Cold Cream

➤ Organoleptic Evaluation

The organoleptic properties like color, odor, physical state, appearance and roughness of the prepared herbal cold cream was evaluated.

➤ Washability

The cream was applied on the hand and observed under the running water.

➤ pH

The pH meter was calibrated with the help of 6.8 standard buffer solution. Weigh 0.5g of prepared cream and dissolve it in 50ml of distilled water and its pH was measured with the help of digital pH meter.^[8]

➤ Viscosity

Viscosity of the herbal cream was determined with the help of Brookfield viscometer at 100 rpm with a spindle number 64.

$$cP = TK \times SMC \times \frac{10000}{RPM}$$

Where,

cP = Viscosity

TK = Torque %

SMC = Spindle multiplier constant.

➤ Spreadability test

The herbal cream sample was applied between the two glass slides and was compressed between the two glass slides to uniform thickness by placing 100g of weight for 5minutes then weight was added to the weighing pan. The time in which the upper glass slide moved over the lower slide was taken as a measure of spread ability.

$$\text{Spreadability} = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Where;

M = weight tied to upper slide

L = length moved on the glass slide

T = time taken to separate the slide

➤ Irritancy test

Mark an area (1sq.cm) on the left hand dorsal surface. The cream was applied to the specified area and time was noted. Irritancy, erythema, edema was checked if any for regular intervals up to 24 hours and reported.^[9]

➤ Homogeneity

The formulations were tested for the homogeneity by visual appearance and by touch.

➤ In vitro diffusion study

Cellophane membrane was used for this study in Frantz Diffusion Cell. 100mg of prepared Ashwagandha, Curcumin and Neem herbal cold cream is placed in donor compartment separately which is filled phosphate buffer 6.8. The membrane was mounted between the compartments of the Frantz Diffusion Cell. Reservoir compartment was filled with the phosphate buffer 6.8. The study was carried out at 37±1⁰ and speed was adjusted to 100-200 rpm and it is carried out for 24 hours. 5ml of sample was withdrawn from each reservoir compartment by the help of hypodermic syringes at half an hour interval for 2 hours, then 1 hour interval for 10 hours and finally 6 hours to next 24 hours and absorbance was measured spectrophotometrically at 422.1nm for Curcumin, 208.5 nm for Ashwagandha and at 320.4nm for Neem. Each time reservoir compartment was replenished with the 5ml fresh volume of phosphate buffer 6.8 pH solution to maintain constant volume.^[10]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:**Results****Characterization of herbal cold cream****Percentage yield:**

Percentage yield of different formulation F1 to F9 were shown in Table No.4

Table No: 4. Percentage yield of F1 to F9 Formulation.

Formulation code	Theoretical yield (gm)	Practical yield (gm)	Percentage yield (%)
F1	50	39.22	78.4
F2	50	39.44	78.8
F3	50	39.94	79.8
F4	50	42.23	84.46
F5	50	42.99	85.98
F6	50	43.75	87.5
F7	50	41.48	82.96
F8	50	42.93	85.86
F9	50	43.74	87.48

SEM studies:

Determination of surface morphology was done by ZEISS EVO. US Scanning electron microscope. The F3, F6 and F9 formulations shows smooth surface characteristics. The SEM images of F3, F6 and F9 formulations are showed in Figure no.1, 2 and 3 respectively.

Fig No: 1. SEM images of formulation F3.

Fig No: 2. SEM images of formulation F6.

Fig No: 3. SEM images of formulation F9.

DSC studies:

The study shows Curcumin properties higher temperature has been exhibited melting point at 186.22⁰ C, Ashwagandha properties higher temperature has been exhibited melting point at 254.06⁰ C and Neem properties higher temperature has been exhibited melting point at 157.21⁰ C. The DSC peaks of F3 formulations has exhibited melting point at 186.22⁰ C and peak is showed in Figure No. 4. The DSC peaks of F6 formulations has exhibited melting point at 257.92⁰ C and peak is showed in Figure No. 5. The DSC peaks of F9 formulations has exhibited melting point at 160.12⁰ C and peak is showed in Figure No. 6.

Figure No: 4. Spectra showing DSC of F3 formulation.

Figure No: 5. Spectra showing DSC of F6 formulation.

Figure No: 6. Spectra showing DSC of F9 formulation.

Evaluation of Herbal cold cream

The prepared Herbal cold cream was evaluated for the above mentioned parameters and the result was observed as follows:

Table No: 5. Evaluation parameters of formulated Herbal cold cream.

Formulations	Colour	pH	Viscosity	Spreadability	Irritancy	Washability
F1	Faint yellow	5.2	32304	20.4	Non irritant	Easily washable
F2	Faint yellow	5.4	38200	21.1	Non irritant	Easily washable
F3	Faint yellow	5.5	40140	22.8	Non irritant	Easily washable
F4	Faint green	5.3	42080	12.99	Non irritant	Easily washable
F5	Faint green	5.7	41789	13.86	Non irritant	Easily washable
F6	Faint green	5.9	40326	15.18	Non irritant	Easily washable
F7	Faint green	5.3	55162	30.1	Non irritant	Easily washable
F8	Faint green	5.5	53542	31.5	Non irritant	Easily washable
F9	Faint green	5.8	41431	32.4	Non irritant	Easily washable

In-vitro diffusion studies:

Table No: 6. In-vitro drug release kinetics of F1 to F9 formulations.

Time (hr)	% Drug Release *								
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.5	2±0.02	4±0.0074	6±0.045	3±0.032	4±0.045	5±0.017	1±0.045	2±0.065	3±0.045
1	7±0.05	10±0.021	13±0.032	9±0.035	12±0.032	14±0.045	4±0.022	6±0.045	8±0.092
1.5	11±0.052	15±0.042	17±0.076	12±0.076	15±0.021	19±0.033	7±0.031	9±0.012	12±0.034
2	14±0.026	19±0.032	23±0.065	14±0.012	18±0.078	21±0.085	11±0.015	14±0.032	17±0.071
3	24±0.065	28±0.054	31±0.032	19±0.062	24±0.041	28±0.047	15±0.023	19±0.011	21±0.061
4	29±0.052	33±0.032	39±0.076	23±0.045	27±0.021	32±0.026	20±0.032	24±0.036	27±0.054
5	33±0.023	38±0.038	43±0.062	29±0.073	33±0.036	37±0.073	29±0.075	34±0.045	38±0.012
6	38±0.012	43±0.014	49±0.034	34±0.046	39±0.046	43±0.071	38±0.064	43±0.037	46±0.037
7	45±0.014	48±0.016	53±0.026	41±0.065	45±0.042	49±0.042	45±0.072	48±0.085	51±0.034
8	52±0.045	54±0.036	59±0.071	48±0.055	52±0.021	56±0.022	49±0.064	54±0.078	59±0.084
9	55±0.075	58±0.074	64±0.064	55±0.036	58±0.076	61±0.071	57±0.072	59±0.021	63±0.061
10	59±0.023	63±0.036	69±0.072	58±0.022	61±0.065	65±0.046	61±0.032	64±0.012	68±0.077
11	63±0.041	67±0.045	72±0.043	63±0.075	66±0.012	70±0.075	68±0.045	70±0.042	73±0.041
12	67±0.042	72±0.031	75±0.032	66±0.065	69±0.065	73±0.011	70±0.078	72±0.081	76±0.061
18	70±0.032	75±0.086	80±0.045	70±0.036	73±0.078	76±0.025	73±0.061	75±0.073	79±0.011
24	74±0.076	78±0.043	83±0.061	74±0.021	76±0.094	80±0.077	75±0.073	79±0.073	82±0.081

*Mean of 9 readings.

Figure No: 7. Graph of In-vitro drug release of F1 to F9 formulations.

DISCUSSION

The SEM images of formulation F3, F6 and F9 reveals that the herbal cold creams are smooth in surface. The F3 formulation has showed an endothermic peak at 186.22⁰ C, whereas F6 formulation has showed a peak at 257.92⁰ C and F9 formulation has showed a peak at 160.12⁰ C. The pure Curcumin have shown an endothermic peak at 186.22⁰ C, whereas Ashwagandha shows peak at 254.06⁰ C and Neem shows peak at 157.21⁰ C due to the melting point of drug but this peak is not exactly seen in drug loaded formulations this indicates the drug was uniformly distributed in formulations. The viscosity of all 9 formulations was in the range of 499990 to 30000 cps, which indicates that the cream is easily spreadable by small amount of shear. The formulations F3, F6 and F9 shows highest pH compare to their other formulations. Change in drug concentration may leads to changes in the pH of preparations. According the result, all the formulations i.e. F1 to F9 showed no sign of irritancy, erythema and edema. It indicates that the prepared herbal cold cream was safe to use and all the formulations i.e. F1 to F9 are easily washable. The F9 formulation shows good spreadability compared to other formulation. The result of *in-vitro* diffusion studies are shown in Table No. 6. The cumulative percentage of drug diffusion from F1 to F9 ranges from 74% to 83%. Formulation F3, F6 and F9 shows highest percentage drug release and from the graph it shows the drug release in 'controlled manner' compared to other formulations.

CONCLUSION

The F3, F6 and F9 formulations shows good percentage yield compare to other and their SEM images shows good results of smooth surface with very small pore size. DSC studies shows that, the drug in F3, F6 and F9 formulations is uniformly distributed and it is amorphous in nature and it shows there is no chemical reactions. All the Herbal cold cream formulations shows pH in the range of 5.2 to 5.9 which is good for skin. The formulations F3, F6 and F9 shows highest percentage of drug release compare to other formulations.

Based on the resultant data obtained from the different evaluation parameters it can be concluded that the prepared formulations were stable and safe to use.

In future, they may further subjected for stability studies and *in-vivo* studies using human voluntaries.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ATR	Automatic terminal recognition
DSC	Differential scanning calorimetry
SEM	Scanning electronic microscopy
RPM	Rotation per minute
UV	Ultra violate
QS	Quantity sufficient

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

Declare none.

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